

Implications in Studies of Adsorption of Isopropanol at the Hg Electrode

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Adsorption of isopropanol on the mercury electrode from HCl of μ_{constant} using electrocapillary data shows that the Frumkin isotherm is followed, but the interaction parameter varies with charge density. The standard free energy of adsorption does not display either a quadratic or linear dependence on charge. By applying the surface pressure model of Parsons it was deduced that the adsorption isotherms are not congruent with respect to charge. Results confirm the change in orientation with increasing coverage due to polarisability effects. The model of the adsorption layer is discussed on the basis of testing the congruence of isotherms with respect to both potential and charge density over the polarisation range studied. The congruence of the isotherms obtained for the adsorption of isopropanol with respect to potential indicates that the adsorption layer is probably represented by a two parallel capacitors model.

THERE are several types of analyses to select whether the free energy of adsorption of an organic compound is a function of charge density or of potential as the electrical variable¹. Molecules that strongly interact with mercury such as thiourea² show a linear variation of the standard free energy of adsorption with charge which was interpreted as a covalent bond formation. Other molecules that weakly adsorb on mercury show a quadratic dependence on charge, e.g. urea³. The choice of the electrical variable determines the model of the adsorption layer⁴; in presence of an adsorbed organic substance the inner layer can be regarded as two series ($\sigma^M = \text{constant}$) or two parallel ($E = \text{constant}$) capacitors.

In a theoretical study of the implications of the medium effect in adsorption studies it has been suggested that a better characterisation is obtained when the surface pressure (ϕ) is employed as a function of the organic content. By avoiding errors that may arise due to medium effects, the adsorption of isopropanol was reported at constant chemical potential of the HCl electrolyte (μ_{HCl})⁵. It is the purpose of this investigation to integrate these results and to determine the adsorption model through the choice of the proper electrical variable.

Results and Discussion

The electrocapillary curves obtained by double integration of capacitance data⁵ were used in calculating the Parsons' function (ξ), $\xi = \gamma + \sigma^M E$, where γ is the surface tension, σ^M the charge density and E the applied potential vs Ag/AgCl electrode. The surface pressure at a constant charge was determined from the expression, $\phi = \xi^b - \xi$, where ξ^b is the value of the Parsons' function in $10^{-2} M$ HCl in absence

of isopropanol at a given charge density σ^M . Fig. 1 shows the lowering of the surface tension vs potential (a), and surface pressure vs charge density (b), respectively (the numbers refer alcohol concentrations as given in Table 1). The potential and charge density of maximum adsorption for isopropanol in solutions of HCl at constant μ as determined from the figure are $-0.6 V$ and $-2.2 \mu C cm^{-2}$.

Esin and Markov plots at constant charge densities are shown in Fig. 2. The plot for $\sigma^M = -2.2 \mu C cm^{-2}$ is a horizontal straight line corresponding to the potential of maximum adsorption (E_{max}). This, together with the results shown in Fig. 1 is a proof that a single charge and a single potential of maximum adsorption exist⁶.

Numerical differentiation of ξ with respect to log concentration of isopropanol provides values of the surface excess Γ . In this calculation, μ_{HCl} is constant. The surface coverage (θ) was calculated from relation, $\theta = \Gamma/\Gamma_{\text{max}}$, where $\Gamma_{\text{max}} = 3.01/10^{14} \text{ mol cm}^{-2}$ (Ref. 5) as obtained by extrapolation of $1/\Gamma$ vs $1/c_{\text{org}}$ to $1/c = 0$. Fig. 3 shows the variation of θ with σ^M ; maximum adsorption is attained for all solutions at $-2.2 \mu C cm^{-2}$ with $\theta \approx 1$ at the maximum concentration used.

The results were found to follow the Frumkin isotherm as given by the relation⁷,

$$\theta/(1-\theta) \exp(-2\alpha\theta) = \beta c$$

where, α is the interaction parameter and β the adsorption coefficient. The agreement between experimental data and the Frumkin isotherm was tested graphically by plotting $\ln \theta/(1-\theta)c$ vs θ at each value of σ^M . Within the experimental error a good linearity of the experimental points was found, indicating the validity of Frumkin's isotherm in the present case. Fig. 4 represents typical tests for

Fig. 1. (a) Lowering of surface tension vs potential and (b) surface pressure vs charge density (alcohol concentrations as given in Table 1).

TABLE 1—ISOPROPNOL SOLUTIONS USED AT CONSTANT μ_{HCl}

Solution no.	Alcohol % (w/w)	Alcohol concn. mol dm^{-3}
1	0	0
2	0.25	0.042
3	0.50	0.083
4	0.75	0.125
5	1.00	0.166
6	1.50	0.250
7	2.00	0.333
8	2.50	0.416
9	3.00	0.499
10	4.00	0.636
11	5.00	0.832
12	7.50	1.248
13	10.00	1.664
14	20.00	3.328
15	30.00	4.993

solutions rich in water and rich in alcohol. It is clear that α , as obtained from the slope, reverses its sign from positive to negative, in agreement with the previous observation at constant potential⁵. The change of the sign of α from negative to positive values was previously reported for 2-methoxyethanol⁶. The present results indicate that at low concentrations of alcohol the adsorbate-adsorbate interaction is high, whereas at higher concentrations the adsorbate-solvent interaction in the interface is stronger than the mean value of adsorbate-adsorbate and solvent-solvent interactions⁹. This may be

Fig. 2. Esin and Markov plots; constant values of σ^M ($\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$) for each line indicated on the figure.

Fig. 3. Variation of surface coverage with charge density

Fig. 4 Test of the Frumkin isotherm at different charge densities. (a) low alcohol concentrations (< 3%) and (b) high alcohol concentrations (> 3%)

correlated with the breaking up of the residual water network in solutions rich in alcohol⁵, in contrast to solutions rich in water which seem to be more structured than in the absence of alcohol¹⁰. Thus, variation in the sign of α may be attributed to polarisability effects due to reorientation of the molecule with increased coverage⁵.

Values of the adsorption coefficient β were obtained from the intercepts in Fig. 4. The standard free energy of adsorption (ΔG_A°) was calculated from the relation, $\beta = \exp(-\Delta G_A^\circ/RT)$. The dependence of ΔG_A° on σ^M is shown in Fig. 5, with a maximum at $-2.2 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$. However, this figure cannot be described as parabolic, and hence a trial to plot $(\Delta G_A^\circ - \Delta G_{A,\text{max}}^\circ)$ vs $(\sigma^M - \sigma_{\text{max}}^M)^2$ or σ^M showed that the standard free energy of adsorption does not display either a quadratic or linear dependence on charge.

Fig. 5. Dependence of ΔG_A° on charge density: (a) low alcohol concentrations (< 3%) and (b) high alcohol concentrations (> 3%).

One of the analyses to select whether the free energy of adsorption is a function of charge density or of potential as the electrical variable is based on the linearity of the plot for the change in σ^M at constant E due to adsorption, or for the change in E at constant σ^M . Fig. 6 shows the former dependence, while a trial to plot the latter relation did not produce good linearity. This indicates that the free energy of adsorption of isopropanol is a function of E , in agreement with the results described earlier⁵, where the quadratic dependence of the free energy of adsorption on E shows that polarisability rather than polarity effects prevail as pointed out by Trasatti¹¹ in the analysis of fundamental parameters in the adsorption of organic compounds.

Fig. 6. Change in charge density due to adsorption of isopropanol at constant E .

To determine the model of the adsorption layer, the surface pressure model of Parsons² was first employed to determine the influence of the electrical field on the isotherms. The values of ϕ were plotted against $\log c$ at constant σ^M . It is clear from Fig. 7 that shifting these plots along the x-axis will not provide superimposable plots due to the apparent difference in curvature at each σ^M . This indicates that the adsorption isotherms are not congruent with respect to charge.

Fig. 7. Surface pressure of isopropanol for different charge densities; constant values of charge density σ^M ($\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$) indicated on the figure.

To test the congruence with respect to potential, the same test was carried out, in addition to a more sensitive test such as plotting Γ vs $y = c/c_{\Gamma=a}$, where $c_{\Gamma=a}$ is the concentration at which a selective value of $\Gamma=a$ is observed. Some typical Γ vs y data at various potentials between -0.1 and -1.0V are shown in Fig. 8. The scatter of points is quite reasonable⁶ in view of the slight variations in the values of α . In calculating the line shown in Fig. 8 which

Fig. 8. Experimental surface excess values at various potentials for isopropanol adsorption on Hg as a function of the relative concentration of the alcohol; line indicates calculated isotherm and points indicate experimental isotherm.

represents the theoretical Frumkin isotherm at $E = -0.3\text{V}$ with the parameters $\Gamma_s = 3.01 \times 10^{14}\text{ mol cm}^{-2}$ (s : saturation), $\alpha = -4$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger = -15.27\text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$ (Ref. 5), the results show some deviations at low alcohol concentrations ($< 3\%$ by weight). The line which actually passes through the experimental points at such concentrations as obtained from tests of the Frumkin isotherm at different potentials⁶, would give a better fit with the parameters $\alpha = 2.5$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger = 0.35\text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$. Such a behaviour agrees with the observation that each concentration range of isopropanol is represented by different parameters due to an assumed reorientation of the molecules as a consequence of polarisability effects⁶ and as ensured by the present results. The congruence of the isotherms obtained for the adsorption of isopropanol at constant μHCl with respect to potential indicates that the most probable model for the adsorption layer is that of two parallel capacitors.

References

1. R. PARSONS, *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1968, **18**, 91.
2. R. PARSONS, *Proc. R. Soc., Ser. A*, 1961, **261**, 79.
3. R. PARSONS, R. PRAT and R. M. REEVES, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1975, **62**, 151.
4. A. N. FRUMKIN, B. B. DAMASKIN and A. A. SURVILA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1968, **16**, 493.
5. A. A. MAZHAR, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1989, **67**, 2102.
6. K. DOBELHOFFER and D. M. MOHILNER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 1698.
7. B. DAMASKIN, O. PETRII and V. BATRAKOV, "Adsorption of Organic Compounds on Electrodes", Plenum, New York, 1971.
8. O. IKEDA, K. KOGO and H. TAMURA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1983, **151**, 163.
9. F. PULIDORI, G. BORGHESANI, R. PEDRIALI, A. DIBATTISTI and S. TRASATTI, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1, 1978, 79.
10. A. MAZHAR, R. BENNES, P. VANEL and D. SCHUHMAN, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1979, **100**, 395.
11. S. TRASATTI, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1974, **53**, 335.